

DISPOSITIVE RIGHTS OF THE VICTIM IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS AND SOME PROBLEMS OF THEIR USE

Rashidov Bekhzod Nurboyevich

Doctor of Law, Associate Professor

Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: *The article sets out the dispositive rights of the victim in the criminal process, the content of criminal procedural rules that reflect dispositive rights, the procedure for using dispositive rights, private prosecution, gaps in the legislation regarding the procedure for proceedings on dispositive grounds and other problems associated with the use of dispositive rights, and an opinion on their decision.*

Keywords: *dispositivity, victim, criminal procedure activity, dispositive rights of the victim, private prosecution.*

Introduction. When comprehending the procedural and legal content of the concept of dispositivity, it is appropriate to pay attention to the “dispositive grounds for the emergence of activity”. Because dispositivity is the right of a person to choose to act and, vice versa (in the presence of presumptions or relations of law) to do nothing. Dependence on the discretion of the victim, the implementation of the action or not, is a dispositive basis for initiating a criminal procedural action.

In our opinion, dispositivity is understood as the discretion of a person in demanding protection and ensuring their rights, the right to choose between demanding protection of violated rights or not.

According to the subject, dispositiveness is divided into two, that is, into material dispositiveness and procedural dispositiveness [1, 45-46]. If material discretion is expressed in the freedom to demand the protection of rights protected

by law, then procedural discretion is expressed in the freedom to use the means of protecting one's interests in criminal proceedings.

Material discretion is manifested in the rights of the victim, as well as the civil plaintiff from the participants in criminal proceedings. In particular, the institution of private prosecution also belongs to material discretion. Procedural discretion can be seen in the rights of all participants defending their interests. The freedom to use the right to appeal a procedural decision is an example of procedural discretion.

The main part. Dispositive rights can also be classified by subject. An analysis of the rights of the subject of optionality allows us to have a broader idea of optionality. Due to the fact that discretion in criminal proceedings is initially manifested in the rights of the victim, it is appropriate to analyze the rights of the victim [2; 3, 51-52].

The following rights of the victim have dispositive content: presentation of evidence; submission and rejection of applications; get a representative to protect their interests; after the completion of the inquiry or preliminary investigation, get acquainted with all the materials of the case and record the necessary information from them, make copies of the materials and documents using technical means at their own expense or record the information contained in them in a different form; filing applications for reconciliation in cases provided for by law; filing complaints against the actions and decisions of an official of the pre-investigation inspection body, an interrogating officer, an investigator, a prosecutor and a court; to support charges in court personally or through a representative; the right to know about the complaints and protests submitted in the case and to raise objections against them.

Rights as a victim to submit petitions for reconciliation in cases provided for by law; to support charges in court personally or through a representative; the right to familiarize with complaints, protests and file objections to them are associated with material discretion. At the same time, the procedure for using the rights of the victim, as well as other citizens, to demand their restoration in case of violation of

the fundamental rights established by the Constitution, is reflected in the criminal procedure legislation. This mechanism is also a material dispositivity. That is, material discretion means that proceedings can be initiated against a person whose rights were affected by an event considered as the basis for criminal procedure, whether it is a crime or not, that is, upon appeal.

In doing so, provide evidence; make motions and challenges; have a representative to defend their interests; after the end of the inquiry or preliminary investigation, get acquainted with all the materials of the case and write out the necessary information from it, make copies of the materials and documents at their own expense or record in another form the information contained in them using technical means; to bring complaints against the actions and decisions of the inquirer, investigator, prosecutor and court according to the content refers to the procedural discretion.

Like the rights of the victim, the rights of the civil plaintiff, the accused, the civil defendant, as well as the rights of other persons defending their interests in the criminal process, have a dispositive content. The rights of the civil plaintiff, as well as the rights of the victim, are divided into substantive and procedural dispositive rights.

The substantive dispositive right is expressed in the discretion to sue for a violation of the right, which is the basis for the proceedings. The dispositive rights of the suspect, the accused and the civil defendant are basically procedural dispositive rights.

Procedural legislation, reflecting the principles of the implementation of activities, through these principles shows its content and priorities. In the days of the former union, the principles that did not take into account the inviolability of private property, as well as the priority of the rights and legitimate interests of the individual, were reflected in the legislation regulated by criminal procedure, as well as in other areas, and the principle of publicity was mainly in effect in the implementation of

legal proceedings. That is, criminal procedural activity is mainly aimed at protecting the interests of the state, state intervention in all spheres of society has been noticed, many functions are mainly assigned to state bodies. As a result, the lack of competition, the lack of public control, the continuation of the performance of their functions by state bodies without taking into account the expediency or necessity of their activities led to a decrease in efficiency and a crisis.

As in other areas, the application of the principles of discretion in criminal procedure activities serves to prevent unnecessary and inappropriate performance of work, avoiding excessive costs. In this regard, A.V.Smirnov, who conducted research on the models of the criminal process, emphasizes that the models, types, forms, types and manifestations of the criminal process were formed and developed under the influence of the conditions of certain historical periods and existed according to a certain need [4, 13-19]. Usually based on the imperative and dispositive methods of regulation of criminal procedure, now in many countries the imperative method of regulation of criminal procedure has priority. In our opinion, the effective use of the dispositive method of activity regulation is of great importance today.

At present, the fact that social processes and economic relations around the world have somewhat accelerated requires that procedural activities, in particular, the procedure for conducting and resolving criminal cases, be relatively simple and can be carried out in a short time. Unfortunately, the current criminal procedure legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the procedure for legal proceedings in accordance with the principle of publicity, and not according to the principle of discretion. As a result, it can be seen that serious problems arise in the fight against crime. Such problems include: when it is advisable to use dispositive rights in the investigation of an incident, make appropriate decisions bypassing or grossly violating the law, since the procedure established by law does not allow this, being forced to cover up a crime, not restoring the rights of ordinary citizens violated

as a result of a crime, violating the legitimate interests of persons involved in procedural activities, inappropriate and inefficient use of public funds, sometimes criminal procedural activities become an obstacle to the development of the economy and other cases.

In our opinion, in order to find an effective solution to the fight against crime, as well as some of the existing problems associated with it, it is advisable to improve the foundations and procedure for criminal procedure, based on the requirements of discretion. According to F.M. Mukhitdinov, in criminal proceedings, private law allows a citizen to independently and freely decide the issue of the emergence, transition and termination of legal relations, without state intervention, and protects him [5, 79]. At the same time, it serves to further expand the application of dispositive norms in criminal proceedings and the development of the institution of private prosecution [6, 40-41].

The institute of private prosecution, reflecting the content of the provision, is regulated by articles 1, 2, 11, 17, 64, 84, 116, 325, 329, 330, 333, 342, 372, 373, 401, 582-586 of the current Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The types of crimes prosecuted as private charges are specified in Article 325 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These include: part one of article 105, article 109, part one of article 110, article 111, part one of article 118, part one of article 119, part one of article 121, article 136, parts one and two of article 139, parts one and two of article 140, part one of article 141-1, article 149. Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, criminal cases against a legal entity that does not have a state share in the authorized capital and committed by its employee, provided for in Articles 167, 170, 172, 173 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are initiated only at the request of the head, owner or authorized management body of this legal entity. At the same time, it can be seen that the elements of private prosecution are more fully reflected in the procedure for the production of criminal cases for these crimes in Article 325 of the

Code of Criminal Procedure, and for which, after the initiation of a criminal case, the victim can be terminated due to reconciliation between the victim and the accused. These include: the crimes provided for in the first part of Article 105 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (intentional bodily injury of medium gravity), in Article 109 (intentional light bodily injury), in the first part of Article 110 (torture), in Article 111 (infliction by negligence of medium gravity or grievous bodily injury), in the first part of Article 121 (forcing a woman to have sexual intercourse), in Article 136 (forcing a woman to marry or preventing marriage), in the first and second parts of Article 139 (slander), in parts one and two of Article 140 (insult), part one of Article 141-1 (violation of privacy), part one of Article 149 (violation of copyright or invention rights), part one of Article 167 (theft by misappropriation or embezzlement), part the first and in paragraphs "b", "c" of the second part of Article 170 (causing property damage by deceit or breach of trust), in Article 172 (bad faith in the protection of property) and in part one of Article 173 (intentional destruction or damage to property). The procedure for conducting cases on crimes specified in Article 325 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, but for which it is impossible to terminate a criminal case by way of conciliation after the initiation of a case, and not specified in Article 325, but for which a criminal case may be terminated on the basis of a conciliation agreement, is private-public or public-private (mixed) accusation.

Today, relations are regulated on the basis of legal norms in all countries, in the period when the first legal norms were established, criminal proceedings were based on a private claim (accusation) [7, 37]. Because before the creation of the state and during the period of the emergence of the first state and law, only at the claim of the plaintiff were proceedings carried out, and sentences or decisions were made. In Muslim law, private prosecution based on Sharia norms was widely practiced [8, 269-273; 9, 107-133].

The procedural order of proceedings on the basis of a private prosecution is not fully defined in the current Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Here it is appropriate to talk about discreteness in law, gaps in the law, as well as gaps in the law regarding the order of private prosecution. Discretion in law [10] is defined as a general concept in the historical context and discreteness in legislation in a purely legal context. That is, it can be understood as breaks in the historical development of law and the absence of links between the mechanisms that make up a certain area of law. According to P.D. Ivanenko, discreteness in the historical context means the interruption of continuity in the gradual development of the legal system, the non-functioning of a specific legal system in a particular state under the influence of internal and external political or internal and external non-political factors, or it exists only in name. Discreteness in legal content means discreteness in legislation, that is, the invalidity of legislative norms, legal regulation, the mechanism for applying the norms, as well as the impossibility of applying existing norms with the operation of the entire legal system [11, 80].

Conclusion. It can be said that the historical discreteness of our legal system manifested itself as a result of the introduction in the last century of a new system, relatively unfamiliar to us, instead of the legal system that we used. At the same time, although private prosecution as a norm existed in the current criminal procedure legislation in the Soviet period, it can be noted that there are gaps in the mechanism for its application or that this legal institution was not used as a discreteness of legislation. In our opinion, the problems associated with the conduct of private prosecution cases at the present time are rooted in gaps and discreteness in the legislation.

Clarification and formalization of the situation of the victim's failure to apply for the commission of crimes under Article 325 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, explanation to the victim of the legal consequences arising from the failure to file an application, the reaction of a person suspected of committing a

crime to a refusal to initiate a criminal case on this basis, and most importantly, questions of their legal status is not clearly regulated in the current legislation. This causes certain difficulties and inconsistencies in the search for a reasonable solution to the problems that arise in the implementation of the activities of practitioners in organizing and conducting an investigation in order to ensure the rights of participants in the process and the legal resolution of materials and cases of this nature.

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10. Discretion – 1) fragmentation of the state of matter (planet you, bodies, crystals, molecules, atoms, nuclei and etc.), the degree of its differentiation in the form of individual stable elements of various systems, qualitatively defined structures by levels; 2) spasmodic character development process, change. Словарь общенаучных терминов / под ред. В. В. Шабанова. – URL: <http://msuee.ru/science/Voc%20OND/SLOVA/5.htm>.

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